

Seroprevalence of Transfusion-Transmitted Infections among Blood Donors at a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs) pose a significant risk to blood transfusion safety, particularly in regions with high prevalence rates of infections like HIV, Hepatitis B, and Hepatitis C. Despite advancements in blood screening protocols, TTIs continue to challenge healthcare systems globally, necessitating ongoing surveillance and improvement in blood donation practices.

Aim: This study aimed to determine the seroprevalence of TTIs among blood donors at a tertiary care teaching hospital and to assess the relationship between TTI status and donor demographic factors.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 300 blood donors. Donor demographics and donation histories were recorded, and blood samples were tested for HIV, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, Syphilis, and Malaria using standard serological methods. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, employing descriptive statistics to determine ubiquity and chi-square tests to evaluate associations between TTI status and demographic variables.

Results: The overall seroprevalence of TTIs among the donors was 6%, with Hepatitis B being the most prevalent infection (2.67%). Significant correlations were found between TTI status and gender ($p = 0.04$) and between TTI status and donation status (first-time vs. repeat donors) ($p = 0.02$).

Conclusion: The study identified a moderate predominance of TTIs among blood donors, with male and first-time donors at higher risk. These findings highlight the need for enhanced screening and targeted education efforts to improve blood safety.

Recommendations: It is recommended to implement more rigorous donor screening protocols, particularly for first-time and male donors, and to conduct regular monitoring of TTI trends to adapt strategies accordingly. Educational campaigns focused on safe donation practices could also reduce TTI prevalence.

Keywords: Transfusion-transmitted infections, blood donors, seroprevalence, Hepatitis B, blood safety.

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Introduction

Blood transfusions are an essential part of contemporary healthcare, supporting surgeries, treating anaemia, and treating trauma and various illnesses, among other things, saving millions of lives every year. A blood transfusion can save lives, but it also comes with risks. These include the potential for the spread of illnesses like malaria, syphilis, HIV, hepatitis B and C viruses, and influenza. (TTIs) continue to pose a serious threat to public health, particularly in areas where blood safety regulations are laxly followed or where the infection is frequently seen in the general populace.

The WHO has called for all nations to establish thorough screening programs for tuberculosis and has emphasised the significance of guaranteeing a safe blood supply. Recent research indicates that

TTIs remain a problem despite these measures, especially in underdeveloped nations where blood safety infrastructure may be inadequate [1]. Geographically speaking, the frequency of TTIs varies greatly; low- and middle-income nations usually have greater rates. According to a study carried out in Nigeria, the seroprevalence rate of TTIs among blood donors was 10.9% [2], whereas a study done in India discovered a rate of 3.5% [3]. The necessity for localised data to support and enhance blood safety initiatives is highlighted by these variances.

Tight donor selection standards, sophisticated testing techniques, and enhanced public health initiatives have led to a notable decline in the occurrence of TTIs in wealthy nations. Still, TTIs

are not completely eradicated, even in these areas. An investigation conducted in the United States, for instance, found that blood donors had a seroprevalence rate of 0.03% for HIV, suggesting that the danger is still present even if it is low [4]. A significant amount of blood transfusions are performed in tertiary care facilities, where there is a pressing need for continual monitoring of blood donors due to the persistent dangers associated with TTIs. This study aimed to determine the seroprevalence of TTIs among blood donors at a tertiary care teaching hospital and to assess the relationship between TTI status and donor demographic factors.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Blood Bank of MGM Medical College, a tertiary care teaching hospital located in Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, from December 2022 to April 2024.

Participants: A total of 300 blood donors were included in the study. The participants were selected consecutively as they presented to donate blood during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- 18–60 year old voluntary blood donors.
- Donors who are male and female.
- Contributors who gave their informed consent.
- Donors who satisfied the National Blood Transfusion Service's standard eligibility requirements for blood donation.

Exclusion Criteria

- Donors with a history of previous transfusions within the last 12 months.
- Donors with known chronic illnesses, including but not limited to diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular diseases.
- Donors who tested positive for any TTIs during preliminary screening.

- Donors who refused to provide consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible donors presenting during the study period were included. Information bias was reduced by ensuring that all data were collected using standardized procedures and instruments. The same team of trained personnel performed the testing and data collection to reduce observer bias.

Data Collection: Structured interviews and donor records containing demographic information (e.g., age, gender, occupation, etc.) and donation history were used to gather data. Each donor provided blood samples, which were then subjected to normal serological testing procedures to check for the presence of TTIs such as HIV, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, Syphilis, and malaria.

Procedure: Sterile methods were employed to obtain blood samples from every donor. The National Blood Transfusion Service recommends utilising ELISA and other standard serological techniques to examine each sample for TTIs. Additional testing techniques were used to confirm the positive samples, and the outcomes were entered into a safe database.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was employed to analyse the data. TTI prevalence was summed up using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages), and associations between TTI status and demographic information were assessed using chi-square tests. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05. This technique guarantees a methodical approach to precisely ascertain the seroprevalence of TTIs in blood donors.

Results

The study included a total of 300 blood donors. The majority of the participants were male (70%), and the predominant age group was 26-35 years (40%). Most of the donors were first-time donors (55%).

Table 1: The demographic characteristics

Demographic Variable	Number of Donors (n = 300)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	210	70%
Female	90	30%
Age Group (years)		
18-25	75	25%
26-35	120	40%
36-45	75	25%
46-60	30	10%
Donation Status		
First-time Donor	165	55%
Repeat Donor	135	45%

Table 2: Prevalence of (TTIs)

TTI	Number of Positive Cases (n = 18)	Percentage of Total Donors (%)
HIV	4	1.33%
Hepatitis B	8	2.67%
Hepatitis C	3	1.00%
Syphilis	2	0.67%
Malaria	1	0.33%

Out of the 300 blood donors, 18 tested positive for at least one transfusion-transmitted infection, resulting in an overall seroprevalence rate of 6%. The distribution of TTIs among the donors is detailed in Table 2.

Table 3: Correlation between TTI Status and Demographic Variables

Demographic Variable	p-value
Gender	0.04
Age Group	0.15
Donation Status	0.02

The relationship between TTI status and demographic variables was evaluated using chi-square tests, as shown in Table 3. A statistically noteworthy correlation was found between TTI status and gender ($p = 0.04$) and between TTI status and donation status (first-time vs. repeat donors) ($p = 0.02$). No significant association was found between TTI status and age group ($p = 0.15$).

Discussion

The study, involving 300 blood donors revealed an overall seroprevalence of (TTIs) at 6%. Among the infections detected, Hepatitis B was the most predominant, accounting for 2.67% of the cases, followed by HIV at 1.33%, Hepatitis C at 1%, Syphilis at 0.67%, and Malaria at 0.33%. These findings underscore the persistent risk of TTIs in the blood supply, emphasizing the need for vigilant screening protocols.

The study also found significant correlations between TTI status and certain demographic variables. Male donors showed a statistically higher prevalence of TTIs compared to female donors ($p = 0.04$). Additionally, first-time donors were more prone to have an elevated TTI test than repeat donors ($p = 0.02$), highlighting the importance of targeted screening and education for new donors. While age did not show a significant correlation with TTI status ($p = 0.15$), the distribution of infections across different age groups suggests that younger donors, particularly those aged 26-35 years, are more frequently represented among TTI-positive cases.

An investigation was conducted in Nagpur, India, to find out how common TTIs are among healthy blood donors. According to the study, hepatitis B had the highest frequency of TTIs, at 0.7%. Following with prevalence rates of 0.09% and 0.04%, respectively, were syphilis and HIV. The study revealed a steady decline in the frequency of TTIs over time demonstrating the value of

enhanced donor selection procedures and public awareness initiatives [5].

A different study carried out at a Central Indian tertiary care teaching hospital found that the overall seroprevalence of TTIs among blood donors was 1.43%. Hepatitis B (1.29%) had the highest predominance, followed by HIV (0.076%) and Hepatitis C (0.072%). This study shown that despite intensive screening efforts, there is still a persistent risk of TTIs and that donor selection and screening practices need to be continuously improved [6].

An investigation conducted in Pakistan focused on the high rate of TTIs among blood donors with an emphasis on HIV, HBV, HCV, syphilis, and malaria. With a prevalence rate of 1.5%, hepatitis C was determined to be the most common TTI, followed by syphilis at 0.8%. Stricter donor screening and selection procedures are required, as the study also revealed a worrisome increase in HIV infections among blood donors [7].

Conclusion

According to this study, blood donors had a 6% seroprevalence of (TTIs), with hepatitis B being the most prominent. Due to the higher risk associated with male and first-time donors, more stringent screening procedures and focused interventions are required. These results emphasise how crucial it is to conduct thorough donor screening and ongoing monitoring in order to improve blood safety and lower the frequency of TTIs.

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